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1. INTRODUCTION

As part of the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) in NANOFACETS, the present Deliverable details all scientific publications from the Consortium up to month 18 of the action. All publications have been deposited into an open repository, and links are provided below. The list of publications is also available from the project website: <https://www.nanofacts.net/publications/>

2. PEER-REVIEWED JOURNALS

The following papers have been published in international peer-reviewed journals (first page of the papers included in the Annex below):

1. Mladenović, M., Morgan, I., Ilić, N., Saoud, M., Pergal, M. V., Kaluđerović, G. N., & Knežević, N. Ž. (2021). pH-Responsive Release of Ruthenium Metallotherapeutics from Mesoporous Silica-Based Nanocarriers. *Pharmaceutics*, 13(4), 460.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics13040460>

Abstract: Ruthenium complexes are attracting interest in cancer treatment due to their potent cytotoxic activity. However, as their high toxicity may also affect healthy tissues, efficient and selective drug delivery systems to tumour tissues are needed. Our study focuses on the construction of such drug delivery systems for the delivery of cytotoxic Ru(II) complexes upon exposure to a weakly acidic environment of tumours. As nanocarriers, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) are utilized, whose surface is functionalized with two types of ligands, (2-thienylmethyl)hydrazine hydrochloride (H1) and (5,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-yl)hydrazine (H2), which were attached to MSN through a pH-responsive hydrazone linkage. Further coordination to ruthenium(II) center yielded two types of nanomaterials MSN-H1[Ru] and MSN-H2[Ru]. Spectrophotometric measurements of the drug release kinetics at different pH (5.0, 6.0 and 7.4) confirm the enhanced release of Ru(II) complexes at lower pH values, which is further supported by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) measurements. Furthermore, the cytotoxicity effect of the released metallotherapeutics is evaluated in vitro on metastatic B16F1 melanoma cells and enhanced cancer cell-killing efficacy is demonstrated upon exposure of the nanomaterials to weakly acidic conditions. The obtained results showcase the promising capabilities of the designed MSN nanocarriers for the pH-responsive delivery of metallotherapeutics and targeted treatment of cancer.

2. Živojević, K., Mladenović, M., Djisalov, M., Mundzic, M., Ruiz-Hernandez, E., Gadjanski, I., & Knežević, N. Ž. (2021). Advanced mesoporous silica nanocarriers in cancer theranostics and gene editing applications. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 337, 193–211.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2021.07.029>

Abstract: Targeted nanomaterials for cancer theranostics have been the subject of an expanding volume of research studies in recent years. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) are particularly attractive for such applications due to possibilities to synthesize nanoparticles (NPs) of different morphologies, pore diameters and pore arrangements, large surface areas and various options for surface functionalization. Functionalization of MSNs with different organic and inorganic molecules,

polymers, surface-attachment of other NPs, loading and entrapping cargo molecules with on-desire release capabilities, lead to seemingly endless prospects for designing advanced nanoconstructs exerting multiple functions, such as simultaneous cancer-targeting, imaging and therapy. Describing composition and multifunctional capabilities of these advanced nanoassemblies for targeted therapy (passive, ligand-functionalized MSNs, stimuli-responsive therapy), including one or more modalities for imaging of tumors, is the subject of this review article, along with an overview of developments within a novel and attractive research trend, comprising the use of MSNs for CRISPR/Cas9 systems delivery and gene editing in cancer. Such advanced nanconstructs exhibit high potential for applications in image-guided therapies and the development of personalized cancer treatment.

3. Lynch, M.J., & Gobbo, O.L. (2021). Advances in Non-Animal Testing Approaches towards Accelerated Clinical Translation of Novel Nanotheranostic Therapeutics for Central Nervous System Disorders. *Nanomaterials*, 11(10), 2632. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11102632>

Abstract: Nanotheranostics constitute a novel drug delivery system approach to improving systemic, brain-targeted delivery of diagnostic imaging agents and pharmacological moieties in one rational carrier platform. While there have been notable successes in this field, currently, the clinical translation of such delivery systems for the treatment of neurological disorders has been limited by the inadequacy of correlating in vitro and in vivo data on blood–brain barrier (BBB) permeation and biocompatibility of nanomaterials. This review aims to identify the most contemporary non-invasive approaches for BBB crossing using nanotheranostics as a novel drug delivery strategy and current non-animal-based models for assessing the safety and efficiency of such formulations. This review will also address current and future directions of select in vitro models for reducing the cumbersome and laborious mandate for testing exclusively in animals. It is hoped these non-animal-based modelling approaches will facilitate researchers in optimising promising multifunctional nanocarriers with a view to accelerating clinical testing and authorisation applications. By rational design and appropriate selection of characterised and validated models, ranging from monolayer cell cultures to organ-on-chip microfluidics, promising nanotheranostic particles with modular and rational design can be screened in high-throughput models with robust predictive power. Thus, this article serves to highlight abbreviated research and development possibilities with clinical translational relevance for developing novel nanomaterial-based neuropharmaceuticals for therapy in CNS disorders. By generating predictive data for prospective nanomedicines using validated in vitro models for supporting clinical applications in lieu of requiring extensive use of in vivo animal models that have notable limitations, it is hoped that there will be a burgeoning in the nanotherapy of CNS disorders by virtue of accelerated lead identification through screening, optimisation through rational design for brain-targeted delivery across the BBB and clinical testing and approval using fewer animals. Additionally, by using models with tissue of human origin, reproducible therapeutically relevant nanomedicine delivery and individualised therapy can be realised.

3. CONFERENCE PAPERS

NANOFACTS has also produced the following papers from contributions to international Conferences:

1. Nikola Knezevic, Minja Mladenovic, Mirjana Mundzic and Aleksandra Pavlovic. Stimuli-Responsive Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Applications in Cancer Theranostics, 2021 MRS Fall Meeting, Abstract Book, SB03.05.10, 30th November-7th December, 2021. Virtual event. <https://zenodo.org/record/6200634#.YrdUP3bMLIU>

Abstract: Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) exhibit highly beneficial features for devising nanosystems applicable in cancer therapy, imaging, or diagnostics. The high surface area of MSN, which can be easily post-synthetically functionalized with different organosilanes, in addition to their structured porosity available for loading cargo molecules, allows a plethora of opportunities for devising multifunctional and multipurpose nanostructures. In this context, our research focuses on devising MSN-based cancer theranostics, containing different modalities for targeting specific cancer microenvironment, and the capabilities for delivering cargo therapeutic molecules upon exposure to the specific conditions of this environment, such as tissue acidosis or elevated concentration of glutathione and other cancer-related biomolecules. Thus, specific surface modification and controlling the release process of therapeutic molecules enables utilization of MSNs as unique facilitators toward enhancing the efficacy and precision of cancer treatment, imaging and sensing.

2. Minja Mladenovic, Mirjana Mundzic, Aleksandra Pavlovic, Nikola Knezevic. Potential of mesoporous silica nanoparticles for applications in targeted treatment of cancer. 5th Congress of the “Serbian Association for Cancer Research – SDIR” with international participation „Translational potential of cancer research in Serbia”, Abstract book, P44, 3rd December, 2021. Virtual event. <https://zenodo.org/record/5769294#.YrdVTHbMLIV>

Background: Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) are being vastly demonstrated in the literature as efficient nanocarriers for cancer therapeutics. Their high surface area (ca. 1000 m²/g), well-structured porosity, versatile possibilities for obtaining nanocarriers of different morphologies, pore diameters and surface characteristics, allow construction of different nanosystems for efficient cancer targeting. **Methods:** In this study, the potential of mesoporous silica nanoparticles for applications in targeted treatment of cancer is presented. **Results:** Our team focuses on construction and surface functionalization of MSN with different moieties for active cancer-targeting. The drug release process can be also controlled through different externally applicable stimuli (eg. light irradiation, magnetic field), or upon exposure to intratumoral conditions such as weakly acidic environment, the elevated concentration of glutathione or other cancer biomarkers. In addition, MSN can be decorated with specific moieties to enable imaging of cancer (eg. magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)), which would enable simultaneous cancer therapy and diagnostics (theranostics). **Conclusions:** Mesoporous silica nanoparticles have substantial potentials for enhancing the efficacy and precision of cancer treatment.

3. Minja Mladenović, Mirjana Mundžić; Aleksandra Pavlović; Nikola Knežević. Anticancer Applications of Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles. 7th Nano Today Conference, 16th- 18th November 2021. Virtual event. <https://zenodo.org/record/5733889#.YrdVpXbMLIV>

Abstract: The capabilities in applying mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) for the construction of different types of nanosystems for simultaneous cancer therapy and diagnostics (theranostics) are widely known in the scientific literature. Their specific characteristics, such as high surface area (ca. 1000 m²/g), well-structured porosity, and versatile surface-functionalization possibilities allow devising a plethora of multifunctional nanostructures.

In this context, our research team works on the synthesis of MSNs of different structures and their surface modification toward enabling active cancer-targeting. These MSNs are loaded with different cargo molecules which can serve different purposes, such as cancer treatment, imaging, or sensing cancer-specific environment and biomolecules. The process of cargo release can be also governed by employing externally applicable stimuli (e.g. light irradiation, magnetic field), or upon exposure to intratumoral conditions such as weakly acidic environment, the elevated concentration of glutathione, or in the presence of other cancer biomarkers. The control over this process allows the application of MSNs as unique facilitators in cancer therapy, imaging and sensing, with substantial benefits for enhancing the efficacy and precision of cancer treatment or for early cancer diagnosis.

4. Aleksandra M. Pavlović, Nikola D. Radnović, Marko N. Panić, Nikola Ž. Knežević, Branislav D. Jović. Investigation of the surface interaction of indole with mesoporous silica using FTIR spectroscopy and hyperspectral imaging, *58th Meeting of the Serbian Chemical Society*, Belgrade, Serbia, June 9-10, 2022 <https://zenodo.org/record/6670042#.YrdWD3bMLIX>

Abstract: The adsorption of indole from carbon tetrachloride solution on mesoporous silica (MS) material was investigated by kinetic FTIR spectroscopic measurements. This result is correlated to the capability of indole N-H to participate in hydrogen bonding with the MS surface. Results of FTIR spectroscopy evidence the presence of indole adsorbed on the surface of MS while the analysis of hyperspectral images reveals the possibility of constructing effective qualitative hyperspectral sensors for indole based on MS as a sensing substrate.

Article

pH-Responsive Release of Ruthenium Metallotherapeutics from Mesoporous Silica-Based Nanocarriers

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Abstract: Ruthenium complexes are attracting interest in cancer treatment due to their potent cytotoxic activity. However, as their high toxicity may also affect healthy tissues, efficient and selective drug delivery systems to tumour tissues are needed. Our study focuses on the construction of such drug delivery systems for the delivery of cytotoxic Ru(II) complexes upon exposure to a weakly acidic environment of tumours. As nanocarriers, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) are utilized, whose surface is functionalized with two types of ligands, (2-thienylmethyl)hydrazine hydrochloride (H1) and (5,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-yl)hydrazine (H2), which were attached to MSN through a pH-responsive hydrazone linkage. Further coordination to ruthenium(II) center yielded two types of nanomaterials MSN-H1[Ru] and MSN-H2[Ru]. Spectrophotometric measurements of the drug release kinetics at different pH (5.0, 6.0 and 7.4) confirm the enhanced release of Ru(II) complexes at lower pH values, which is further supported by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) measurements. Furthermore, the cytotoxicity effect of the released metallotherapeutics is evaluated in vitro on metastatic B16F1 melanoma cells and enhanced cancer cell-killing efficacy is demonstrated upon exposure of the nanomaterials to weakly acidic conditions. The obtained results showcase the promising capabilities of the designed MSN nanocarriers for the pH-responsive delivery of metallotherapeutics and targeted treatment of cancer.

Keywords: pH-responsive drug delivery; mesoporous silica nanoparticles; ruthenium-based anti-cancer drugs; controlled drug delivery; cancer treatment

1. Introduction

Cancer treatments typically cause a range of side effects [1,2], induced by poor selectivity for cancerous over healthy cells, and researchers are making a significant effort to develop methodologies for controlled and site-specific drug delivery to cancer [3,4]. Towards this end, the application of nanomaterials is seen as very encouraging [5,6], particularly due to the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect, which enables selective accumulation of nanoparticles at tumour tissues [7]. Moreover, some nanomaterials, such as mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) allow the employment of additional cancer-targeting modalities, through devising nanocarriers with stimuli-responsive drug delivery capabilities [8]. Further beneficial attributes of MSN include their large surface area, uniform mesoporosity, tunable morphology, facile surface functionalization and proven biocompatibility [9–11].

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Review article

Advanced mesoporous silica nanocarriers in cancer theranostics and gene editing applications

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ABSTRACT

Targeted nanomaterials for cancer theranostics have been the subject of an expanding volume of research studies in recent years. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) are particularly attractive for such applications due to possibilities to synthesize nanoparticles (NPs) of different morphologies, pore diameters and pore arrangements, large surface areas and various options for surface functionalization. Functionalization of MSNs with different organic and inorganic molecules, polymers, surface-attachment of other NPs, loading and entrapping cargo molecules with on-desire release capabilities, lead to seemingly endless prospects for designing advanced nanoconstructs exerting multiple functions, such as simultaneous cancer-targeting, imaging and therapy. Describing composition and multifunctional capabilities of these advanced nanoassemblies for targeted therapy (passive, ligand-functionalized MSNs, stimuli-responsive therapy), including one or more modalities for imaging of tumors, is the subject of this review article, along with an overview of developments within a novel and attractive research trend, comprising the use of MSNs for CRISPR/Cas9 systems delivery and gene editing in cancer. Such advanced nanoconstructs exhibit high potential for applications in image-guided therapies and the development of personalized cancer treatment.

1. Introduction

Precise and simultaneous personalized chemotherapy is a long-sought research goal in the battle against all types of cancer. This research is driven by different side effects, which are known to occur regularly in all currently applied chemotherapy regimens against cancer. Conventional chemotherapies use highly toxic and reactive molecules as drugs, which may react with the healthy tissues but also exert wide interindividual pharmacokinetic variability with 2–10-fold variations in exposures after standard doses of cytotoxic drugs [1]. Thus, a large portion of introduced drugs may not be capable of reaching the desired cancer tissue, leading to increasing the dosages of chemotherapeutics and subsequently to enhancing their adverse effects. Therefore, a constant balancing between enhancing the activity of drugs and minimizing their undesirable effects, along with inclusion of other drugs for damage mitigation is driving formulations for conventional therapies. Even though novel types of molecular drugs are being developed for targeted cancer therapies, designed to interact selectively with specific

features of cancer tissues, these targeted therapies may still be inefficient due to tumor heterogeneity, development of drug resistance and other factors related to unpredictable properties of tumor physiologies in different patients [2].

Developing drug delivery systems (DDS) to overcome limitations and enhance the specificity of anticancer drugs is an ever expanding research area [3–5]. Controlled DDS, aimed at localizing the release and effect of therapeutics, have attracted particular attention [6–8]. A promising strategy to enhance the effectiveness of “precision oncology” lies in combining several cancer-targeting modalities. This may be achieved through application of carefully designed nanocarriers, which may be functionalized with different cancer-specific ligands, aimed to selectively deliver cancer therapeutics, along with simultaneous capabilities for cancer imaging. Different types of nanomaterials are being developed for cancer treatment, with several liposomal, one albumin-based nanovesicle and one hafnium oxide-based nanoparticle approved for clinical use and numerous nanoparticles based on liposomes, proteins, polymers, iron oxide and silica undergoing clinical trials [9,10]. The

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Review

Advances in Non-Animal Testing Approaches towards Accelerated Clinical Translation of Novel Nanotheranostic Therapeutics for Central Nervous System Disorders

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Abstract: Nanotheranostics constitute a novel drug delivery system approach to improving systemic, brain-targeted delivery of diagnostic imaging agents and pharmacological moieties in one rational carrier platform. While there have been notable successes in this field, currently, the clinical translation of such delivery systems for the treatment of neurological disorders has been limited by the inadequacy of correlating *in vitro* and *in vivo* data on blood–brain barrier (BBB) permeation and biocompatibility of nanomaterials. This review aims to identify the most contemporary non-invasive approaches for BBB crossing using nanotheranostics as a novel drug delivery strategy and current non-animal-based models for assessing the safety and efficiency of such formulations. This review will also address current and future directions of select *in vitro* models for reducing the cumbersome and laborious mandate for testing exclusively in animals. It is hoped these non-animal-based modelling approaches will facilitate researchers in optimising promising multifunctional nanocarriers with a view to accelerating clinical testing and authorisation applications. By rational design and appropriate selection of characterised and validated models, ranging from monolayer cell cultures to organ-on-chip microfluidics, promising nanotheranostic particles with modular and rational design can be screened in high-throughput models with robust predictive power. Thus, this article serves to highlight abbreviated research and development possibilities with clinical translational relevance for developing novel nanomaterial-based neuropharmaceuticals for therapy in CNS disorders. By generating predictive data for prospective nanomedicines using validated *in vitro* models for supporting clinical applications in lieu of requiring extensive use of *in vivo* animal models that have notable limitations, it is hoped that there will be a burgeoning in the nanotherapy of CNS disorders by virtue of accelerated lead identification through screening, optimisation through rational design for brain-targeted delivery across the BBB and clinical testing and approval using fewer animals. Additionally, by using models with tissue of human origin, reproducible therapeutically relevant nanomedicine delivery and individualised therapy can be realised.

Keywords: nanotheranostics; blood–brain barrier; advanced drug delivery; *in vitro* modelling; organ-on-chip; *in silico* testing

Citation: Lynch, M.J.; Gobbo, O.L. Advances in Non-Animal Testing Approaches towards Accelerated Clinical Translation of Novel Nanotheranostic Therapeutics for Central Nervous System Disorders. *Nanomaterials* 2021, 11, 2632. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11102632>

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1. Introduction

The diagnosis and treatment of central nervous system (CNS) disorders constitute a notable challenge in the field of modern therapeutics and advanced drug delivery systems, and it would appear such disorders are on the rise despite increasing appreciation and elucidation of underlying aetiology and pathophysiological mechanisms [1,2]. The CNS therapeutics market is set to grow to EUR 114.4 billion in 2025, and a resurgence in the neuroscience field is predicted, which will be bolstered by novel drug delivery systems and new chemical entities (NCE's). The most recent global burden of disease (GBD) study published in the *Lancet* journal shows that the global burden of neurological disorder approaches the 14% value of overall disease modelled over a decade ago, accounting